

14. KONGRES FARMAKOLOGA I
4. KONGRES KLINIČKE
FARMAKOLOGIJE SRBIJE
sa međunarodnim učešćem

14th SERBIAN CONGRESS OF
FARMACOLOGISTS AND
4th SERBIAN CONGRESS OF
CLINICAL PHARMACOLOGY
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14. KONGRES FARMAKOLOGA SRBIJE
4. KONGRES KLINIČKE FARMAKOLOGIJE SRBIJE

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4th SERBIAN CONGRESS OF CLINICAL
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Rezultati su pokazali da kombinacija metformina i nitroglicerina značajno menja patohistološke karakteristike fibrosarkoma hrčaka, uključujući Ki-67-pozitivnost i imunoekspresiju citoplazmatskih markera, bez indikacija toksičnosti. Primena metformina u kombinaciji sa nitroglicerinom inhibira proliferaciju fibrosarkoma *in vivo*, što ukazuje da ova kombinacija može biti kandidat za novu efikasnu, sigurnu i netoksičnu antikancersku adjuvantnu terapiju ili terapiju prevencije relapsa.

Zahvalnost: Ovo istraživanje finansirao je Pokrajinski sekretarijat za visoko obrazovanje i naučnoistraživačku delatnost AP Vojvodine [br. 142-451-2413/2018 (JP)] i Ministarstvo prosvete, nauke i tehnološkog razvoja Republike Srbije [br. 171039 (JS) i 172013 (DM)].

PATHOHISTOLOGICAL CHANGES IN EXPERIMENTAL FIBROSARCOMA TUMORS OF HAMSTERS TREATED WITH METFORMIN AND NITROGLYCERIN

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The anticancer effects of metformin and nitroglycerin were investigated. The immunohistochemistry of experimental fibrosarcoma tumors was investigated in hamsters treated with metformin and nitroglycerin. The hamsters were injected with BHK-21/C13 cells in order to induce fibrosarcoma, and the animals were treated daily with metformin, nitroglycerin or a combination of the two drugs. Subsequently, blood samples were obtained for biochemical analyses and the tumors were excised. The tumor samples were pathohistologically and immunohistochemically assessed for proliferation marker protein Ki-67, hematopoietic progenitor cell antigen CD34, cytochrome *c* oxidase subunit 4 (COX4), glucose transporter 1 (GLUT1) and inducible nitric oxide synthase (iNOS), and vital organs were toxicologically tested. Ki-67-positivity and cytoplasmic marker (CD34, COX4, GLUT1, iNOS) immunoexpression in the tumor samples were quantified. The results revealed that the combination of metformin and nitroglycerin significantly altered the pathohistological characteristics of the hamster fibrosarcoma tumors, including Ki-67-positivity and the immunoexpression of cytoplasmic markers, without indications of toxicity. In conclusion, the administration of metformin in combination with nitroglycerin may inhibit fibrosarcoma proliferation *in vivo*, suggesting that this may be an effective and safe approach as a nontoxic anticancer adjuvant and relapse prevention therapy.

Acknowledgements: This study was supported by the Republic of Serbia, Autonomous Province of Vojvodina, Provincial Secretariat for High Education and Scientific Research [grant no. 142-451-2413/2018 (JP)] and Republic of Serbia, Ministry of Science [grant nos. 171039 (JS) and 172013 (DM)].

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FIZICKO-HEMIJSKE PROMENE EKSPERIMENTALNIH FIBROSARKOMA KOD HRČAKA TRETIRAANIH METFORMINOM I NITROGLICERINOM

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U ovom eksperimentu, ispitivani su ankancerski efekti poznatih registrovanih neokoloških lekova metformina i nitroglicerina. Analizirani su težina, prečnici, zapremina, gustina, površina i odnos površine prema zapremini eksperimentalnih fibrosarkoma kod hrčaka tretiranih metforminom i nitroglicerinom. Hrčkovima su injicirane BHK-21/C13 ćelije da bi se indukovao fibrosarkom, i životinje su tretirane svakodnevno metforminom, nitroglicerinom ili kombinacijom ova dva leka. Nakon toga su prikupljeni uzorci krvi za biohemijske analize, tumori su ekscizovani, a njihova težina, prečnici i zapremina izmereni. Vitalni organi su toksikološki analizirani. Rezultati su pokazali da kombinacija metformina i nitroglicerina značajno menja fizičko-hemijske karakteristike fibrosarkoma kod hrčaka, uključujući apsolutnu i relativnu težinu, zapreminu, gustinu, dužinu, površinu i odnos površine prema zapremini, bez indikacija toksičnosti. Primena metformina u kombinaciji sa nitroglicerinom inhibira rast fibrosarkoma *in vivo*, što ukazuje da ova kombinacija može postati kandidat za novu efikasnu, sigurnu i netoksičnu antikancersku adjuvantnu terapiju ili terapiju prevencije relapsa.

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PHYSICOCHEMICAL CHANGES IN EXPERIMENTAL FIBROSARCOMA TUMORS OF HAMSTERS TREATED WITH METFORMIN AND NITROGLYCERIN

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The anticancer effects of metformin and nitroglycerin, which are established non-oncologic drugs, were investigated in the present study. The weight, diameter, volume, density, surface and surface to volume ratio of experimental fibrosarcoma tumors were investigated in hamsters treated with metformin and nitroglycerin. The hamsters were injected with BHK-21/C13 cells in order to induce fibrosarcoma, and the animals were treated daily with metformin, nitroglycerin or a combination of the two drugs. Subsequently, blood samples were obtained for biochemical analyses and the tumors were excised, weighed and measured. Vital organs were toxicologically tested. The results revealed that the combination of metformin and nitroglycerin significantly altered the physicochemical characteristics of the hamster fibrosarcoma tumors, including absolute and relative weight, volume, density, length, surface area and surface to volume ratio, without indications of toxicity. In conclusion, the administration of metformin in combination with nitroglycerin may inhibit

the growth of fibrosarcoma tumors *in vivo*, suggesting that this may be an effective and safe approach as a nontoxic anticancer adjuvant and relapse prevention therapy. *Acknowledgements:*

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EFEKAT MEBENDAZOLA NA MELANOM

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Melanom je najopasnija forma kancera kože koja je u mnogim slučajevima rezistentna na konvencionalnu hemoterapiju. Iz tog razloga predstavlja izazov za istraživanje novih terapijskih pristupa. Lekovi koji su odobreni za korišćenje u različitim indikacijama, a poseduju prethodno ne prepoznatu citiotoksičnost prema malignim ćelijama mogli bi se brzo koristiti i u ovoj novoj indikaciji. Novi podaci sugerišu da bi jedan od ovakvih lekova sa novom indikacijom mogao biti mebendazol. Mebendazol pripada grupi benzimidazola, to su antihelmintici koji se široko koriste u humanoj i veterinarskoj medicini. Mebendazol se dobro toleriše a koristi se od ranih 1970-ih godina za lečenje infekcija gastrointestinalnim parazitima. On deluje tako što inhibira polimerizaciju mikrotubula vezujući se za rastući kraj mikrotubula. Ispitivali smo efekat mebendazola na humane i mišje melanomske ćelije *in vitro* i mišje melanomske ćelije *in vivo*. Ustanovili smo da mebendazol inhibira preživljavanje i da ima proapoptotski efekat na ćelije melanoma *in vitro*. Per oralna primena mebendazola kod miševa sa melanomom dovodi do usporavanja rasta tumora. Ovi rezultati su ohrabrujući za dalja istraživanja jer mebendazol ima izvanredan bezbednosni profil i dobru podnošljivost.

THE EFFECT OF MEBENDAZOLE ON MELANOMA

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Melanoma, the most serious type of skin cancer is in most cases resistant to conventional chemotherapy. Because of that it represents a great challenge for investigation of new therapeutic approaches. Drugs approved for indications other than cancer that possess previously unrecognized cytotoxicity toward malignant cells could be rapidly used for this new indication. New data suggest that one of these drugs with new indication could be mebendazole. Benzimidazole anthelmintics including mebendazole are widely used